

SLOSHING EFFECTS ON FREE-BODY COMMERCIAL AIRCRAFT AEROELASTIC LOADS

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Abstract. The study presents the effect of nonlinear sloshing on internal loads experienced by commercial aircraft during severe gust excitations. The numerical approach consists of a hybrid modelling in which the aeroelasticity is approached via standard differential equations obtained by a modal description of the aircraft and a rational function approximation of the unsteady aerodynamic operator provided by an off-the-shelf aeroelastic solver, whereas the nonlinear behavior of the fluid stowed in the wing tanks is described via data-driven black-box model. More specifically, the black-box model consists of a neural network trained via experimental data on scaled problem. The model is then used to study the gust response of an Airbus provided research aircraft model via a verified scaling law that allows to integrate the model in different aircraft configuration.

Introduction

Aircraft are generally subjected to a wide range of loads during flight and ground operations that cause significant deformation of the wings, especially during the most severe loading phases. This can lead to sloshing of the fuel stowed in the wing tanks, whose weight is comparable to that of the structural components. The interaction between the fuel dynamics and the structure of the aircraft can in turn influence its performance, affecting both stability and response to external loads. This work is framed within the H2020 project SLOshing Wing Dynamics (SLOWD), which studies fuel sloshing as a method to reduce loads in aircraft wings by increasing effective damping.

The effects of sloshing on the aeroelastic flutter stability of aircraft were discussed in several works Refs. [1,2] where liquid dynamics was modelled using equivalent mechanical models (EMMs), frozen fluids and linear frequency domain approaches. Furthermore, the effects of sloshing on aeroelastic typical section behavior has been investigated in Ref. [3] by direct time-marching analysis employing Smoothed Particle Hydrodynamics (SPH). However, this works were aimed at modelling only the lateral and rotational behavior of sloshing fluid thus neglecting the dissipative impact that vertical sloshing can have on the aircraft loads.

The objective is to study how sloshing affects the aeroelastic response of an aircraft under high perturbations by employing reduced-order models (ROMs) that can accurately replicate the forces generated by fuel motion. High-amplitude sloshing, more specifically, is described by only involving accelerations perpendicular to the liquid free surface. Rather than providing a coupling between the dynamics of the free surface and the rest of the system, vertical sloshing

can be regarded as a kind of energy sink. Several activities demonstrated this concept either by experimental fluid-structure interaction tests via sloshing beam (See Ref. [4]) and via experimental identification of sloshing damping performances in harmonic regimes across different value of amplitude and motion frequency (see Ref. [5]). For small tank vertical accelerations, the free surface tends to remain flat. As the amplitude of the oscillations increases, symmetrical standing waves appear while, for vertical accelerations greater than the acceleration of gravity, the system goes into Rayleigh-Taylor instabilities, which may determine a turbulent flow regime inside the cavity. The impacts of the liquid with the tank ceiling following the free surface fragmentation cause additional dissipation of energy, which in the overall balance of elastic potential energy and fluid energy leads to a noticeable increase in the effective damping of the structural motion. The need for fast simulations pushed towards the implementation of two class of reduced-order models. The first one is a data-driven physical model based on the idea that sloshing behaves as a bouncing ball inside the tank (See Refs. [6,7]), the second class fully relies on data (See Refs [8,9]). Based on time series generated by a scaled experiment, the vertical sloshing ROM is built with a nonlinear finite impulse response (NFIR) network model, a neural-network-based model that is effective in reproducing the nonlinear dynamic behavior of

(a)

(b)

Figure 1 Aeroelastic/sloshing modelling of the Airbus provided research aircraft model.

vertical sloshing (See Ref. [8]). This work aims at studying the gust response of a free-body commercial aircraft considering sloshing dynamics following the studies that were performed on a single aisle research wing configuration in Ref. [10].

Hints on the aeroelastic/sloshing modelling

The aeroelastic/sloshing modelling follows the formulation introduced in Ref. [11] and it is implemented in a Simulink® environment as illustrated in Fig. (1a). The aeroelastic blocks are purely differential whereas the sloshing block is modelled with the identified data-driven neural-network-based ROM. The simulation model implements the following equation in modal coordinates:

$$M \ddot{q} + Kq = e + g + f \quad (1)$$

in which e is the vector of generalized aerodynamic forces, f is the vector of external forces the sloshing forces g are the loads predicted by the neural network, following the history of the modal velocity evaluated at the tank positions. The aeroelastic system is modelled by employing the finite element method (FEM) to obtain the structural modes of the beam and by generating a lifting surface based on the doublet lattice method (DLM) discretization method for the unsteady aerodynamics. The aeroelastic analysis is based on the modes of vibration of the dry structure. Based on these, the FE solver also allows for computation of the generalized aerodynamic force (GAF) matrices for Mach number and reduced frequency k pairs provided by the user. To achieve a purely differential formulation for the unsteady aerodynamics, a rational function approximation (RFA) based on Roger interpolation method is applied to the GAF matrix, resulting in the definition of a new set of aerodynamic finite states. The numerical model also incorporates a block that allows the gust to be included as an external input acting on the aeroelastic system. Fig. (1b) presents the stick model of the research aircraft model provided by Airbus that is used as numerical testbed for the present analysis. Twenty modes of vibrations are used for the analyses including 6 rigid body modes.

Results at a glance

The simulations were performed using a standard 1-cosine gust profile. To keep the model confidential, the parameters of the analysis are not defined and the data in the figure are normalized. Fig. (2a) shows the acceleration at the wing tip whereas Fig.(2b) shows the response in terms of wing-root bending moment. It can be noticed that sloshing provides an acceleration and loads alleviation due to the damping effect provided by sloshing fluid in the tank.

Figure 2 Tip acceleration and wing-root bending moment between frozen and sloshing models.

Conclusions

The study aimed to assess the influence of nonlinear sloshing on the internal loads experienced by commercial aircraft during severe gust excitations. Employing a numerical approach that combined differential and data-driven modeling techniques, the research examined the aircraft accelerations and internal loads of a research aircraft model provided by Airbus. The findings highlighted the significant role played by liquid sloshing in alleviating loads, thereby offering insights into the potential application of such analyses to facilitate less conservative aircraft design approaches.

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